

NOTES

Molecular Interaction of Some Nonpolar Liquids with Dimethylsulphoxide. Osmotic coefficient and activity of solvent (DMSO) in Solution*

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DEPRESSION in freezing point in solutions of some nonpolar nonelectrolyte solutes namely benzene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and cyclohexane have been determined at different concentrations. The osmotic coefficient and activity of the solvent was

calculated from freezing point depression data. The activity of the solvent tends to unity at infinite dilution in all the cases indicating that all solutions approach the ideal behaviour at infinite dilution.

The osmotic coefficient in all systems are nearly unity even at higher concentrations. This shows the absence of self association of these organic liquids in DMSO; also these systems do not appear to show any deviations from Rault's law. It indicates an appreciable dipole-induced dipole interaction between solute and solvent molecules which causes the solute molecules to remain unassociated.

In our previous studies¹, the molecular interactions between DMSO and some polar liquid like methanol,

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF SOLUTE AND OSMOTIC COEFFICIENT AND ACTIVITY OF SOLVENT IN SOLUTIONS

Solute and its normal mol. wt(M_0)	Molality 'm'	Depression in freezing point ΔT	Apparent molecular weight M	Osmotic coefficient (ϕ) of DMSO	Activity (a) of DMSO
Benzene $M_0 = 78.11$	0.1863	0.74	78.26	0.993	0.986
	0.2635	1.00	81.92	0.948	0.981
	0.3215	1.23	81.21	0.956	0.976
	0.4231	1.59	82.82	0.939	0.969
	0.4670	1.77	82.02	0.948	0.966
	0.6041	2.24	82.83	0.927	0.957
Toluene $M_0 = 92.14$	0.0386	0.15	94.84	0.986	0.997
	0.0774	0.31	92.00	1.006	0.994
	0.1687	0.67	92.79	0.991	0.982
	0.2139	0.85	92.74	0.992	0.983
	0.2856	1.14	92.32	1.000	0.978
	0.4533	1.82	91.79	1.004	0.965
Carbontetra- chloride ($M_0 = 153.82$)	0.1742	0.68	156.83	0.976	0.987
	0.2689	1.05	156.78	0.976	0.979
	0.3521	1.73	124.59	1.228	0.967
	0.4344	1.73	153.72	0.996	0.967
	0.5279	2.15	150.32	0.019	0.958
	0.6546	2.70	148.43	1.031	0.949
Cyclohexane $M_0 = 84.16$	0.1003	0.40	84.39	1.000	0.992
	0.1901	0.75	85.17	0.986	0.986
	0.2819	1.10	86.32	0.975	0.979
	0.3047	1.20	85.39	0.983	0.977
	0.4552	1.82	84.19	1.000	0.956
	0.4722	1.89	84.09	1.001	0.964

* Presented at the convention of Chemists, 1976

ethanol, cyclohexanol, chlorobenzene and nitrobenzene have been worked out from cryoscopic measurements. All the polar liquids are found to be unassociated in DMSO showing a strong dipole-dipole interaction in solution. It seems therefore, very interesting to see how nonpolar liquids behave in DMSO because question of dipole-dipole interaction does not arise in case of nonpolar liquids. Some nonpolar liquids namely benzene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and cyclohexane are chosen for the present studies, and osmotic coefficient and the activity of solvent (DMSO) is determined in solutions of these liquids from cryoscopic measurements.

Experimental

DMSO (Fluka, purum grade) and all other liquids were used after purification in the manner described earlier².

The simple Beckman apparatus was used for measuring depression in freezing point (ΔT) in solutions. The rest of the procedure for measuring depression in freezing point and calculating apparent molecular weight of solute and osmotic coefficient and activity of solvent was as given in our previous studies¹.

Results and Discussion

The values of apparent molecular weight of solute, osmotic coefficient ' ϕ ' and activity 'a' of solvent (DMSO) in different systems at different concentrations are given in Table 1.

It may be noted from Table 1 that all the solutes have nearly normal molecular weights in DMSO. Since the solutions used are not very dilute, hence there is erratic change in the apparent molecular weight of the solutes.

Osmotic coefficients in all systems are nearly unity at higher concentrations. This shows the absence of self molecular association of these organic liquids in DMSO; also these systems do not appear to show any deviations from Raoult's law. It indicates an appreciable dipole-induced dipole interaction between solute and solvent molecules which causes the solute molecules to remain unassociated.

The activity of the solvent in different solutions decreases as the concentration of the solute in the solution increases. From the activity (a) data given in Table 1, 'a' vs m curves were drawn. Same type of straight line is observed in all cases. On extrapolating the straight lines to zero concentration, activity of solvent is found to be unity in every case, showing that solutions become more ideal in dilute range.

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References

1. D. K. AGARWAL and S. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (under process)
2. R. GOPAL, D. K. AGARWAL and S. AGARWAL, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1976, 8, 801.

Chemical Investigation on Some Mangrove Species Part IV. *Heritiera minor*, a typical Mangrove species

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IN continuation of our earlier report¹⁻³ on ecological influence on taxonomic variation, we report herein the chemical investigation of the leaves and barks of *Heritiera minor* (Fam. Sterculiaceae), a typical Mangrove species of Sundarban. It is a small tree with blend root sucker. The plant materials were collected in the month of December. No chemical work appears to have been reported on this genus.

Petroleum extract of the leaves was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction yielded waxy materials, yet to be characterised. The neutral part on column chromatography over silica gel G yielded the following fractions.

The first fraction furnished a solid material (0.25g), m.p. 245°, $C_{30}H_{60}O$ (M^+426). IR absorption at 1715 cm^{-1} , mass fragmentation pattern and NMR signals showed its identity with friedelin; oxime, m.p. 286°.

Second fraction was triacontanol (0.07g), m.p. 82°.

Third fraction which registered intense spot with Rf 0.42 (solvent: chloroform) on repeated recrystallisations from benzene-alcohol yielded two crystalline materials, compounds A (0.70g) and B (3.50g). Compound A had m.p. 268°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} 0^\circ$, $M^+ 3400$ (-OH), 1635 and 812 cm^{-1} (double bond); M. S. m/e 426(M^+); acetate, m.p. 300°, and was identified as taraxerol. Compound B, m.p. 195°, isolated from the filtrate of compound A was purified through preparative tlc. Superimposable IR spectrum and co-glc on 3% SE-30 on gas chrome-Z, 60-80 mesh (Ret. time: 17.0 mins at 250° - 52°) showed its identity with β -amyryn.

The last fraction was β -sitosterol, m.p. 138°. The bark of *H. minor* on similar work-up showed the presence of all the constituents of leaves with lower yield in each case.

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